

ROSA LIND FRANKLIN
UNIVERSITY
of MEDICINE AND SCIENCE

BOXER LIBRARY

CREATING A STUDENT FOCUSED LIBRARY THROUGH A STUDENT LIBRARY ADVISORY GROUP

BY CLARESSA SLAUGHTER, MSLIS

Methods and Introduction

In this presentation, we will discuss

- Our background and experience with forming a Student Library Advisory Committee (SLAC)
- Steps, hurdles, and future plans when organizing our SLAC

Forming a Student Library Advisory Group

Collaborating with SLAC

Putting Student Feedback into Action

University and Library Background

- Rosalind Franklin University of Medicine and Science (RFUMS) is a small Graduate Health Sciences University located in North Chicago, IL.
- Our library serves all six colleges within the institution:
 - Chicago Medical School
 - Dr. William M. Scholl College of Podiatric Medicine
 - College of Pharmacy
 - College of Health Professions
 - College of Nursing
 - School of Graduate and Postdoctoral Studies

Our Student Library Advisory Committee

When

- Established a decade ago

Who

- Co-chaired by our Education and Curriculum Librarian, Claressa Slaughter and our Associate Vice President, Charlotte Beyer, with collaboration from our Library Associate Director, Carol Ng-He

What

- We use our SLAC as a student focus group and to strengthen student and library relations

Forming a Student Library Advisory Group

| What has worked for us

- **Communication Streams:** We advertise the SLAC sign-up in the library's quarterly newsletter
- **Partnerships:** We reach out to our current student workers, Student Affairs Deans in each college, and past members
- **Events:** We promote SLAC during New Student Orientation sessions
- **Expectations:** We communicate the basic expectations of SLAC in all of our promotional efforts

Hurdles and Future Solutions

- **Hurdles**

- Student turnover
- Recruitment challenges
- Availability

- **Future Solutions**

- Formalized application process
- Dedicated library web presence
- Incentives

2025 - 2026

Student Library Advisory Committee Interest Form

Student Library Advisory Committee (SLAC) Interest Form 25/26

This form is to express interest in SLAC. We are looking for students in their first or second year of their program in each college.

As a member of SLAC you will have the opportunity to

- Shape our library space, services, and resources
- Plan library events
- Act as a liaison between the library and our students
- And more!

At this time we have openings for:

- 1 first or second year student in the College of Health Professions
- 1 -2 first or second year student(s) in the College of Nursing
- 1 first or second year student in the Dr. William M. Scholl School of Podiatry

[You can also check out SLAC's current projects here](#)

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* Indicates required question

SLAC Interest Form Questions

1. What is your name?
2. What is your affiliated college?
3. What year of your program are you in?
4. In 1-2 sentences, why would like to be a part of SLAC?
5. If selected as a SLAC member, I agree to participate in at least three meetings in the academic year: Y/N
6. Do you have any questions about SLAC?

Collaborating with SLAC

| What has worked for us

- **Meeting Frequency:** We require three meetings with one supplemental opportunity, providing additional opportunities for students to get involving
- **Focused Feedback:** We send out forms and surveys before meetings to gather focused feedback and prepare for discussion
- **Dedicated Open Forum:** We set aside dedicated time for students to have an open forum to bring up issues or trends they've noticed in the library

Hurdles and Future Solutions

- **Hurdles**

- Time constraints
- Biased student feedback

- **Future Solutions**

- Communicate projects upfront
- Operational transparency
- Bringing our observations to SLAC

Collaborations for this year

Putting Student Feedback Into Action

How SLAC has Shaped a Student Centered Library

- **Resources:** Whiteboards, external DVD players, a 24 hour study pack, outlets
- **Space:** Feedback used in a space planning committee to advocate for more study spaces
- **Policy:** Students frequently ask for a cafe, which has led us to let students eat in the library
- **Instruction:** Created drop in sessions based on student interest
- **Events and Outreach:** Creation of an “Affirmation Banner” and Student Wellness Weeks events

Hurdles and Future Solutions

- **Hurdles**

- Budget
- Managing student expectations

- **Future Solutions**

- Creative and collaborative compromise

Collaboration in Action

Student Ideas

Library Action

24 Access to Checkouts

A “study pack” with a few popular items that can be accessed 24/7

A Cafe in the Library

Students can eat in the library as long as they clean up after

A SLAC Planned Event

More involvement in established events

Contact Information

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Citations

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